

TERMS TASAVVUF (ILMI KHAL) IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The article analyzes Sufism and its currents, aspects related to the study of Sufism terms in Uzbek linguistics. A linguistic review of the meaning of the term "mysticism" is also given, comments on this term itself, interpretation of interpretations in close terms, and not in sacred books, analysis of literature on the nature of signs and symbols. At the same time, the author of the article tries to draw a conclusion based on the views of scientists and theorists, such as Sheikh Muhammadsadiq Muhammad Yusuf, Navoi scientist Ibrahim Khakkul, Khamidulla Boltaboev, Najmiddin Komilov.

Keywords: Sufism in Islam and its place in human perfection, the term "Sufism" and its linguistic interpretation, interpretation of the symbols of Sufism and symbols in the sources.

Sufism is a trend in Islam that leads the spiritual world of a person to spiritual and moral perfection. The word "at-tasawwuf", according to the most correct opinion, comes from the word "al-musafat" (sincerity between two, purity). It describes the spiritual state in which the Sufi resides with his Patron - Allah (Glorious is He and Exalted), he takes care of the purity of this state and cleanses it of dirt [1].

There are those who connected this word with the word "as-suf" (wool), because the ascetics and people from the past communities, who zealously worshiped Allah, usually wore coarse woolen clothes.

Any theory about the origin of this word is connected with sincere aspiration to Allah and purity in relationship with Him. This is the doctrine of purification, which refers to the purification of the soul, the purification of the soul and the training of the soul. Speaking of Sufism, it is permissible to quote the thoughts of Muhammad Nurullah Sayyid al-Jazari. In the work "Secrets of Sufism" he expressed the following thoughts: "This is a very useful and independent science, reforming the spiritual world of a person, the most effective for the treatment of broken souls, gathering a person around the truth." Entry into the science of Sufism begins with the implementation of the five rules of Islam.

"Tasawwuf" means Sufism. There is much debate about the dictionary meaning of the word "mysticism". Because everyone interprets this concept in their own way.

In Al-Aqida Wash-Shariat fil Islam, researched by Muhammad Yusuf Musa, it is mentioned that Nicholson found 75 definitions of Sufism from works written before the fifth century AH. Abdul Kahir al-Baghdadi found about a thousand definitions in the writings of reliable mystics.

The book “Kavoidut-Tasavuf” mentions that the famous Sufi sheikh Ahmad Zarruq, may Allah bless him and welcome him, gave about 2000 definitions. All of them are in the sense of true worship of Allah, ” said Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf in his book “The Imagination of Sufism” [2].

The terms "Sufi" ("Sufi") and "tasawuf" are inseparable concepts. But there are different interpretations of the origin of these words. Some say that the word "Sufi" comes from the words "suffa", "saf", "safa", "surf" or from the name of Sufa ibn Udd ibn Tlobikha, who in ancient times was a lot of worship. they give comments about the origin. However, to call all this a detailed and correct explanation is inappropriate. From the point of view of Arabic vocabulary, it is more similar that the word "Sufi" comes from the word "surf". According to Ibn Khaldun, the dictionary meaning of the word "surf" is "fur, wool". That is, Sufis are “those who wear clothes made of wool.” We know that in ancient times those who are much mentioned wore clothes made of ordinary woolen cloth. One tradition says that "He wore a garment of wool" in memory of Muhammad, May God bless him and grant him peace. This narration once again emphasizes that the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) was an eternal person.

It can be said that the term "mysticism" does not occur either in the Qur'an or in the hadiths. But although not the term itself, there was another concept that had the same meaning. In the Holy Qur'an there is a word "tazkiyah", which literally means "purification". This was among the four things brought by the Messenger of God, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him. These four sciences were:

reading verses of the Qur'an to mortal servants;

Teachings from the Quran;

Training in the practice of circumcision;

Clear them.

The study and development of the theoretical foundations of Sufism took shape at the beginning of the 9th century. And along with this, the concepts of TARIQAT, ENLIGHTENMENT, TRUTH appeared, and Sufism began to develop as a whole science[3]. Isn't the concept of SHARIA compatible with these concepts? Questions naturally arise as to why Sharia is not included in this list.

It is unacceptable to contradict Sharia and Tariqa and not to distinguish between them. There have been many conflicts and internal conflicts between the people of Shariah and Tariqah since time immemorial. But one thing should be remembered that it is difficult to achieve Tariqa without Sharia. The main idea of the Yassawiyyat tariqa

is: “There is no tariqa without Sharia, there is no enlightenment without tariqa, and there is no truth without enlightenment. They complement each other.” We all know that Sharia works on the basis of “knowledge”, and Tariqa works on “knowledge”. The main sources for both are Kalamullah and Hadith Sharif. Alisher Navoi also divided the sciences into 2 groups, i.e. the science taught in the madrasah is "external" science, and the science of the sect - "hal" - internal sciences. There are many metaphorical and literal descriptions of these mystical states in Sufi sources. For example,

About Sufis and scholars, Rifai (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) says: “The end of scholars and Sufis is one. What the Sufis have achieved with a lot of prayers and a little knowledge, the scholars achieve with a lot of knowledge and a little prayer.”

Sufi terms, symbols, symbols are often found in the Uzbek language, literature and art. Various scholars have tried to study the true meaning and purpose of Sufism, and this continues to this day. Scholars are writing more and more works and treatises on the meaning, functions, terms and symbols of tasavvuf. Such books as “Return to Navoi” by the Navoi scholar Ibrahim Hakkul[4, 5], “Imagination of Sufism” by Sheikh Muhammadsadyk Muhammad Yusuf, “The Origins of Islamic Sufism” by Hamidulla Boltaboev[6], “Tasavvuf” by Najmiddin Komilov serve as scientific guidance in the study. Sufism. In the hadith Sharif: “Scientists are the heirs of the prophets!” This is not in vain said. That is why mystical scholars give us explanations of every term,

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